

LINEAR GEOMETRY: SPECIAL AUTOMORPHISMS OF LINERS

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ABSTRACT. Linear Geometry describes geometric properties that depend on the notion of a line. Objects of study of Linear Geometry are liners, which are sets of points endowed with families of subsets called lines and satisfying two axioms, one of which is the first Euclid axiom (saying that any distinct points belong to a unique line). In this survey paper we study special automorphisms of liners (dilations, translations, and hypershears), and also some special bijections between lines in affine and projective liners (line translations, line affinities, line perspectivities, line projectivities).

INTRODUCTION

This paper is the fourth survey in the series of surveys that describe the contents of the monograph “Linear Geometry and Algebra” [1]. The first survey [2] concentrated at properties of liners that depend on flat hulls (flats, ranks, regularity, parallelity), the second survey [3] discussed completions and projectivizations of lines, the third survey [4] was devoted to Desarguesian, Pappian and Thalesian liners. In this survey we study some special automorphisms of liners: dilations, translations, and hypershears. Also we analyse the structure of some special bijections between lines in affine or projective liners. For affine liners such special bijections are line projections and their finite compositions, and for projective liners special bijections between lines are line projectivities and line perspectivities. The material of this survey covers Chapters 12, 13, 15, 22 of the book [1].

1. PRELIMINARIES

In this section we recall the basic notions of Linear Geometry, needed for understanding the main results of this survey.

A *liner* is a set X of *points*, endowed with a family \mathcal{L} of subsets of X called *lines* such that the following two axioms are satisfied:

- any two distinct points belong to a unique line;
- any line contains at least two distinct points.

A liner X is *κ -long* for a cardinal κ if every line L in X has cardinality $|L| \geq \kappa$.

Let (X, \mathcal{L}) be a liner. For two distinct points $x, y \in X$ we denote by \overline{xy} the unique line containing those points. If $x = y$, then we put $\overline{xy} := \{x\} = \{y\}$.

A subset $A \subseteq X$ is called *flat* if $\overline{xy} \subseteq A$ for any points $x, y \in A$. For a subset $A \subseteq X$ its *flat hull* \overline{A} is the smallest flat set in X that contains the set A . The *rank* $\|A\|$ of a set $A \subseteq X$ is the smallest cardinality of a subset $B \subseteq X$ such that $A \subseteq \overline{B}$. Flat subsets of rank 3 in a liner are called *planes*.

A liner X is *ranked* (resp. *κ -ranked* for a cardinal number κ) if for any distinct flats $A \subset B$ of finite rank (with $\|B\| \leq \kappa$) we have $\|A\| < \|B\|$.

Let κ and λ be cardinals. A liner X is defined to be *κ -balanced* with $|X|_\kappa = \lambda$ if every flat $F \subseteq X$ of rank $\|F\| = \kappa$ has cardinality $|F| = \lambda$. A liner X is called *κ -balanced* if it is κ -balanced with $|X|_\kappa = \lambda$ for some cardinal λ . A liner X is *balanced* if it is κ -balanced for all cardinals κ .

For two flats A, B in a liner X , we say that A is *subparallel* to B and write $A \parallel B$ if $A \subseteq \overline{B \cup \{a\}}$ for all $a \in A$. We say that flats $A, B \subseteq X$ are *parallel* and write $A \parallel B$ if $A \parallel B$ and $B \parallel A$. It is easy to see that two lines L, Λ in a 3-ranked liner are parallel if and only if either $L = \Lambda$ or $L \cap \Lambda = \emptyset$ and $\overline{L \cup \Lambda}$ is a plane.

A bijective map $F : X \rightarrow Y$ between two liners (X, \mathcal{L}_X) and (Y, \mathcal{L}_Y) is called a *liner isomorphism* if $\mathcal{L}_Y = \{F[L] : L \in \mathcal{L}_X\}$. An *automorphism* of a liner X is any liner isomorphism $F : X \rightarrow X$. The set $\text{Aut}(X)$ of automorphisms of a liner X endowed with the operation of composition is a group, called the *automorphism group* of the liner X .

The automorphism group $\text{Aut}(X)$ of a liner X is a subgroup of the inverse monoid \mathcal{I}_X consisting of all bijections between subsets of X . For two bijections $F, G \in \mathcal{I}_X$ their composition is the bijection $F \circ G = \{(x, z) \in X \times X : \exists y \in X (x, y) \in G \wedge (y, z) \in F\}$. A bijection $F \in \mathcal{I}_X$ is called a *line bijection* of a liner X if $\text{dom}[F]$ and $\text{rng}[F]$ are lines in X . Line bijections of X are elements of the monoid \mathcal{I}_X^{ℓ} consisting of the identity map of X and all bijections between flats of rank ≤ 2 in X .

Each subset $A \subseteq X$ of a liner (X, \mathcal{L}) carries the line structure

$$\mathcal{L}_A := \{L \cap A : L \in \mathcal{L} \wedge |L \cap A| \geq 2\}$$

turning A into a liner, called a *subliner* of the liner (X, \mathcal{L}) .

Definition 1.1. A liner X is called

- *strongly regular* if for every nonempty flat $A \subseteq X$ and point $b \in X \setminus A$, we have $\overline{A \cup \{b\}} = \bigcup_{a \in A} \overline{a b}$;
- *regular* if for every flat $A \subseteq X$ and points $o \in A$, $b \in X \setminus A$ we have $\overline{A \cup \{b\}} = \bigcup_{a \in A} \bigcup_{y \in \overline{o b}} \overline{a y}$;
- *weakly regular* if for every flat $A \subseteq X$ and points $o \in A$, $b \in X \setminus A$ we have $\overline{A \cup \{b\}} = \bigcup_{a \in A} \{o, a, b\}$.

Next, we recall some Parallellity Postulates and Axioms.

Definition 1.2. A liner X is defined to be

- *Proclus* if for every plane $P \subseteq X$, line $L \subseteq P$ and point $x \in P \setminus L$ there exists at most one line Λ in X such that $x \in \Lambda \subseteq P \setminus L$;
- *Bolyai* if for every plane $P \subseteq X$, line $L \subseteq P$ and point $x \in P \setminus L$ there exists a line Λ in X such that $x \in \Lambda \subseteq P \setminus L$;
- *Playfair* if for every plane $P \subseteq X$, line $L \subseteq P$ and point $x \in P \setminus L$ there exists a unique line Λ in X such that $x \in \Lambda \subseteq P \setminus L$.

The Parallel Postulates are tightly related to the following Parallellity Axioms.

Definition 1.3. A liner X is defined to be

- *projective* if $\forall o, x, y \in X \ \forall p \in \overline{x y} \ \forall v \in \overline{o y} \setminus \{p\} \ (\overline{v p} \cap \overline{o x} \neq \emptyset)$;
- *proaffine* if $\forall o, x, y \in X \ \forall p \in \overline{x y} \setminus \overline{o x} \ \exists u \in \overline{o y} \ \forall v \in \overline{o y} \setminus \{u\} \ (\overline{v p} \cap \overline{o x} \neq \emptyset)$;
- *affine* if $\forall o, x, y \in X \ \forall p \in \overline{x y} \setminus \overline{o x} \ \exists u \in \overline{o y} \ \forall v \in \overline{o y} \ (u = v \Leftrightarrow \overline{v p} \cap \overline{o x} = \emptyset)$;
- *hyperaffine* if $\forall o, x, y \in X \ \forall p \in \overline{x y} \setminus \overline{o x} \ \exists u \in \overline{o y} \ (\overline{u p} \cap \overline{o x} = \emptyset)$.

By [1, 3.3.17], every affine liner X is 2-balanced. The cardinal $|X|_2$ (equal to the cardinality of any line in X) is called the *order* of the affine liner X . By [1, 3.3.24], every 3-long projective liner X is 2-balanced. The cardinal $|X|_2 - 1$ is called the *order* of the projective liner X . By [1, 3.4.1], a liner is projective if and only if it is strongly regular.

Definition 1.4. A liner X is called

- an *affine space* if X is 3-long, affine, regular and has rank $\|X\| \geq 3$;
- a *projective space* if X is 3-long, projective, and has rank $\|X\| \geq 3$.

A *projective completion* of a liner X is any 3-long projective liner Y containing X as a subliner such that $Y \setminus X \neq Y$. The set $Y \setminus X$ is called the *horizon* of X in Y . More information on projective completions of liners can be found in Chapter 8 of the monograph [1].

An important example of a projective completion is the spread completion of a completely regular liner. Spread completions of liners are introduced and studied in Chapter 7 of the monograph [1]. Here we briefly recall that the definition of the spread completion of a 3-ranked liner.

Let X be a liner and \mathcal{L} be the family of all lines in X . A subfamily $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathcal{L}$ is called a *spread of lines* in X if every point $x \in X$ belongs to a unique line $L \in \mathcal{S}$. A line $L \in \mathcal{L}$ is called *spreading* if the family $L_{\parallel} := \{\Lambda \in \mathcal{L} : \Lambda \parallel L\}$ is a spread of lines in X such that $L_{\parallel} = \Lambda_{\parallel}$ for every line $\Lambda \in L_{\parallel}$. In this case, the spread of parallel lines L_{\parallel} is called a *direction* in the liner X . Let \mathcal{S} be the family of all spreading lines in X . The family $\partial X := \{L_{\parallel} : L \in \mathcal{S}\}$ is called the *boundary* of the liner X . So, the boundary of X consists of all directions in X . For a plane $\Pi \subseteq X$, let $\partial \Pi = \{L_{\parallel} : L \in \mathcal{S} \wedge L \subseteq \Pi\}$ be the *boundary* of the plane Π in X . Let \mathcal{P} be the family of planes Π in X such that $|\partial \Pi| \geq 2$.

If the liner X is 3-ranked¹, then the set $\bar{X} = X \cup \partial X$ endowed with the family of lines

$$\bar{\mathcal{L}} := \{L \cup \{L_{\parallel}\} : L \in \mathcal{S}\} \cup \{\partial \Pi : \Pi \in \mathcal{P}\}$$

is a liner, called the *spread completion* of the liner X . A liner X is called *completely regular* if X is 3-ranked and its spread completion \bar{X} is strongly regular (= projective).

By Corollary 7.6.10 and Theorems 7.6.2 in [1], for every liner we have the implications:

affine regular \Rightarrow strongly regular \Rightarrow completely regular \Rightarrow regular \Rightarrow weakly regular.

A liner X is called

- *Desarguesian* if for any plane $\Pi \subseteq X$, distinct lines A, B, C in Π and any distinct points $o \in A \cap B \cap C$, $a, a' \in A$, $b, b' \in B$, $c, c' \in C$, the set $T := (\overline{a b \cap a' b'}) \cup (\overline{b c \cap b' c'}) \cup (\overline{a c \cap a' c'})$ has rank $\|T\| \in \{0, 2\}$;
- *Pappian* if for any concurrent lines L, L' in X and any distinct points $a, b, c \in L \setminus L'$, $a', b', c' \in L' \setminus L$, the set $T := (\overline{a b' \cap a' b}) \cup (\overline{b c' \cap b' c}) \cup (\overline{a c' \cap a' c})$ has rank $\|T\| \in \{0, 2\}$;
- *Thalesian* if for every plane $\Pi \subseteq X$, any disjoint lines $A, B, C \subseteq \Pi$ and points $a, a' \in A$, $b, b' \in B$, $c, c' \in C$, the equalities $\overline{a b \cap a' b'} = \emptyset = \overline{b c \cap b' c'}$ implies $\overline{a c \cap a' c'} = \emptyset$.

By [1, 10.4.5], every 3-long proaffine regular liner X of rank $\|X\| \neq 3$ is Desarguesian; by Hesserberg's Theorem [1, 20.5.1], every Pappian proaffine regular liner is Desarguesian; by [1, 11.1.5], every Desarguesian Proclus liner is Thalesian. Therefore, for every Proclus liner we have the implications: Pappian \Rightarrow Desarguesian \Rightarrow Thalesian.

2. DILATIONS OF AFFINE LINERS

Definition 2.1. An automorphism $A : X \rightarrow X$ of a liner X is called a *dilation* if for every line L in X , the line $A[L]$ is parallel to L .

Proposition 2.2 ([1, 12.1.2]). *Let X be a proaffine regular liner. The set $\text{Dil}(X)$ of dilations of X is a normal subgroup in the automorphism group $\text{Aut}(X)$ of X .*

Let $F : X \rightarrow X$ be a self-map of a set X . A point $x \in X$ is called a *fixed point* of the map F if $F(x) = x$. We denote by

$$\text{Fix}(F) := \{x \in X : F(x) = x\}$$

the set of fixed points of the map F .

Theorem 2.3 ([1, 12.1.4]). *Every non-identity dilation $A : X \rightarrow X$ of a liner X of rank $\|X\| \geq 3$ has at most one fixed point.*

Proposition 2.4 ([1, 12.1.5]). *If a completely regular liner X admits a non-identity dilation, then X is Playfair.*

Theorem 2.3 motivates the following classification of dilations.

¹A liner X is 3-ranked, if any two planes $A \subseteq B$ in X are equal.

Definition 2.5 ([1, 12.1.8]). A non-identity automorphism $A : X \rightarrow X$ of a liner X is called

- (1) a *translation* of X if A is a dilation of X having no fixed points;
- (2) a *homothety* of X if A is a dilation of X having a unique fixed point o called the *centre* of the homothety.

By definition, the identity automorphism of X is both a translation and a homothety of X .

3. TRANSLATIONS

This section is devoted to studying translations of liners. Given any automorphism $A : X \rightarrow X$ of a liner X , consider the family of flats

$$\overline{A} := \{\overline{xy} : xy \in A\}.$$

It is easy to see that an automorphism $A : X \rightarrow X$ is the identity automorphism of X if and only if \overline{A} is the family of all singletons in X .

Proposition 3.1 ([1, 12.2.1]). *For every nonidentity translation $T : X \rightarrow X$ of a liner X , the family \overline{T} is a spread of lines in X such that $T[L] = L$ for every $L \in \overline{T}$. If the liner X is 3-ranked, then \overline{T} is a spread of parallel lines in X .*

Proposition 3.2 ([1, 12.2.2]). *Let T be a non-identity translation of a liner X . For every $n \in \mathbb{N}$ with $T^n \neq 1_X$, the spreads of lines $\overline{T^n}$ and \overline{T} coincide.*

Proposition 3.3 ([1, 12.2.4]). *Let X be a Proclus liner of rank $\|X\| \geq 3$. Two translations $A, B : X \rightarrow X$ are equal if and only if $A(x) = B(x)$ for some point $x \in X$.*

Proposition 3.4 ([1, 12.2.6]). *Let X be a proaffine regular liner of rank $\|X\| \geq 3$. The set $\text{Tra}(X)$ of translations is a normal subgroup of the automorphism group $\text{Aut}(X)$ of X .*

A group G is called *elementary* if there exists a prime number p such that $g^p = 1$ for every $g \in G$. For affine planes the following theorem is usually attributed to Reinhold Baer.

Theorem 3.5 (Baer; [1, 12.2.7]). *Let X be a proaffine regular liner. If $\|\{T(o) : T \in \text{Tra}(X)\}\| \neq 2$ for some point $o \in X$ (and the group $\text{Tra}(X)$ contains a non-identity element of finite order), then the group $\text{Tra}(X)$ is commutative (and elementary).*

A group G is called *divisible* if the equality $x^n = g$ has a solution in the group G for every $g \in G$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

Problem 3.6 ([1, 12.2.12]). *Let X be a proaffine regular liner such that $\|\{T(o) : T \in \text{Tra}(X)\}\| \geq 3$ for some point $o \in X$, and every non-identity translation of X has infinite order in the group $\text{Tra}(X)$. Is the group $\text{Tra}(X)$ divisible?*

The following theorem shows that the condition $\|\{T(o) : T \in \text{Tra}(X)\}\| \neq 2$ is essential in Theorem 3.5. The idea of the proof of this theorem was suggested by Yoav Krauz in his answer to the problem <https://mathoverflow.net/q/467100/61536>, posed by the author at MathOverflow.

Theorem 3.7 ([1, 12.2.13]). *For every infinite group G , there exists a Playfair plane X of cardinality $|X| = |G|$ such that $\text{Dil}(X) = \text{Tra}(X)$ and the group $\text{Dil}(X) = \text{Tra}(X)$ is isomorphic to the group G .*

Remark 3.8. The first example of a Playfair plane with non-commutative group of translations was constructed by Günter Pickert [7].

Theorem 3.7 suggests two open problems.

Problem 3.9 ([1, 12.2.18]). *Let G be a finite group. Is there a (finite) Playfair plane X whose translation group $\text{Tra}(X)$ is isomorphic to the group G ?*

Problem 3.10 ([1, 12.2.19]). *Let G be a group. Is there a Playfair plane X such that $\text{Aut}(X) = \text{Tra}(X)$ and the group $\text{Aut}(X) = \text{Tra}(X)$ is isomorphic to the group G ?*

4. TRANSLATION AND DILATION LINERS

Definition 4.1. A liner X is called a *translation* if for every points $x, y \in X$ there exists a translation $T : X \rightarrow X$ such that $T(x) = y$.

Proposition 4.2 ([1, 12.3.3]). *Every translation (Proclus) liner X is Bolyai (and Playfair).*

Theorem 4.3 ([1, 12.3.4]). *Every translation Proclus liner is Thalesian.*

Theorem 4.4 ([1, 14.4.8]). *A 3-long affine regular liner is translation if and only if it is Thalesian.*

Theorem 3.5 implies the following corollary.

Corollary 4.5 ([1, 12.3.6]). *The translation group $\text{Tra}(X)$ of any translation proaffine regular liner X of rank $\|X\| \geq 3$ is commutative.*

For every point o in a proaffine regular liner X , the set

$$\text{Dil}_o(X) := \{D \in \text{Dil}(X) : D(o) = o\}$$

is a subgroup of the dilation group $\text{Dil}(X)$. The definition of a translation implies the equality $\text{Dil}_o(X) \cap \text{Tra}(X) = \{1_X\}$.

Proposition 4.6 ([1, 12.3.7]). *Let X be a translation proaffine regular liner of rank $\|X\| \geq 3$. For every point $o \in X$,*

$$\text{Dil}(X) = \text{Tra}(X) \cdot \text{Dil}_o(X) = \text{Dil}_o(X) \cdot \text{Tra}(X)$$

and the group $\text{Dil}_o(X)$ is isomorphic to the quotient group $\text{Dil}(X)/\text{Tra}(X)$.

Example 4.7 ([1, 12.3.8]). There exists a Playfair plane X with $|X|_2 = 9$ whose translation group is trivial and the dilation group $\text{Dil}(X)$ has only two elements. This space contains a unique point $o \in X$ such that $\text{Dil}(X) = \text{Dil}_o(X)$ and for every point $p \in X \setminus \{o\}$ we have $\text{Dil}_p(X) = \text{Tra}(X) \neq \text{Dil}(X)$.

Definition 4.8. A liner X is called a *dilation liner* if for every distinct collinear points $x, y, o \in X$ there exists a dilation $D : X \rightarrow X$ such that $Dox = oy$.

Theorem 4.9 ([1, 16.8.5]). *An affine liner X is dilation if and only if X is Desarguesian.*

5. CENTRAL AND PARACENTRAL AUTOMORPHISMS OF LINERS

Definition 5.1. Let $A : X \rightarrow X$ be an automorphism of a liner X . A point $c \in X$ is called a *centre* of the automorphism A if $A[\overline{xc}] = \overline{xc}$ for every point $x \in X$. An automorphism A of a liner X is called *central* if it has a centre.

Example 5.2. Every point $c \in X$ of a liner X is a centre of the identity automorphism $1_X : X \rightarrow X$.

Proposition 5.3 ([1, 12.4.3]). *Let X be a liner of rank $\|X\| \geq 2$. A non-identity automorphism $A : X \rightarrow X$ can have at most one centre.*

Theorem 5.4 ([1, 12.4.6]). *An automorphism $A : X \rightarrow X$ of a (3-ranked hyperaffine) liner X is central if (and only if) A is a homothety.*

A family of lines \mathcal{F} in a liner X is called

- *concurrent* if $\exists c \in X \ \forall L \in \mathcal{F} \ (c \in L)$;
- *parallel* if $\forall L, \Lambda \in \mathcal{F} \ (L \parallel \Lambda)$;
- *paraconcurrent* \mathcal{F} is parallel or concurrent.

Proposition 5.5 ([1, 12.4.7]). *An automorphism $A : X \rightarrow X$ of a 3-long liner X of rank $\|X\| \geq 3$ is central if and only if the family of lines $\overline{A} := \{\overline{xy} : xy \in A \setminus 1_X\}$ is concurrent.*

Definition 5.6. An automorphism $A : X \rightarrow X$ of a liner X is called *paracentral* if the family $\overline{A} := \{\overline{xy} : xy \in A \setminus 1_X\}$ is parallel. A spread of parallel lines containing the family \overline{A} is called a *central direction* of the paracentral automorphism. A non-identity paracentral automorphism A of a liner X can have at most one central direction, which will be called *the central direction* of X .

Theorem 5.7 ([1, 12.4.10]). *An automorphism $A : X \rightarrow X$ of a 3-ranked liner X is a translation if and only if A is paracentral and $\text{Fix}(A) \in \{\emptyset, X\}$.*

Proposition 5.8 ([1, 12.4.11]). *Let Y be a projective completion of a 3-long 3-ranked liner X of rank $\|X\| \geq 3$, and $A : Y \rightarrow Y$ be an automorphism of the projective space Y such that $A[X] = X$. The automorphism $A : Y \rightarrow Y$ of Y is central if and only if the automorphism $A|_X : X \rightarrow X$ of X is central or paracentral.*

6. HYPERFIXED AUTOMORPHISMS OF LINERS

Definition 6.1. An automorphism $A : X \rightarrow X$ of a liner X is called a *hyperfixed* if its set of fixed points

$$\text{Fix}(A) := \{x \in X : A(x) = x\}$$

contains a hyperplane of X .

Example 6.2. The identity automorphism of any liner is hyperfixed.

In the following proposition, by a *space* we understand any 3-long regular liner of rank ≥ 3 .

Proposition 6.3 ([1, 12.5.4]). *If a non-identity automorphism $A : X \rightarrow X$ of a proaffine space X is hyperfixed, then its set of fixed point $\text{Fix}(A)$ contains a unique hyperplane H . Moreover, $|\text{Fix}(A) \setminus H| \leq 1$.*

Proposition 6.4 ([1, 10.5.6]). *Let $A : X \rightarrow X$ be a hyperfixed automorphism of a proaffine regular liner X . If $\text{Fix}(A)$ is not a hyperplane in X , then the automorphism A is central.*

Theorem 6.5 ([1, 12.5.7]). *Every hyperfixed automorphism of a proaffine space is central or paracentral.*

Theorem 6.6 ([1, 12.6.1]). *An automorphism $A : X \rightarrow X$ of a projective space X is central if and only if A is hyperfixed.*

Corollary 6.7 ([1, 12.6.6]). *An automorphism $A : X \rightarrow X$ of a (non-affine) completely regular space X is hyperfixed (if and) only if A is central or paracentral.*

7. HYPERFIXED AND PARACENTRAL AUTOMORPHISMS OF AFFINE SPACES

Proposition 7.1 ([1, 12.7.1]). *Every hyperfixed automorphism $A : X \rightarrow X$ of an affine space X is paracentral and hence $\text{Fix}(A)$ is a flat in X .*

Definition 7.2. A hyperfixed automorphism $A : X \rightarrow X$ of an affine space X is called a

- a *hypershear* if for every point $x \in X \setminus \text{Fix}(A)$ and its image $y := A(x)$, the line \overline{xy} is subparallel to the flat $\text{Fix}(A)$;
- a *hyperscale* if for every point $x \in X \setminus \text{Fix}(A)$ and its image $y := A(x)$, the line \overline{xy} is not subparallel to the flat $\text{Fix}(A)$.

Definition 7.2 implies that the identity map of an affine space is both a hypershear and a hyperscale. Also Definition 7.2 and Proposition 7.1 imply the following (trivial) classification of hyperfixed automorphisms of affine spaces.

Proposition 7.3 ([1, 12.7.3]). *An automorphism $A : X \rightarrow X$ of an affine space X is hyperfixed if and only if A is a hypershear or a hyperscale.*

Proposition 7.4 ([1, 12.7.4]). *An automorphism $A : X \rightarrow X$ of an affine space X is paracentral if and only if A is a translation, a hypershear or a hyperscale.*

8. SHEAR AND HYPERSYMMETRIC LINERS

Definition 8.1. A liner X is called a *shear liner* if for every hyperplane $H \subseteq X$ and distinct points $x, y \in X \setminus H$ with $\overline{xy} \cap H = \emptyset$, there exists an automorphism $A : X \rightarrow X$ of X such that $A(x) = y$ and $\text{Fix}(A) = H$.

Theorem 8.2 ([1, 12.8.2]). *Every shear affine regular liner is translation.*

A bijection F of a set X is called *involutive* if $F(F(x)) = x$ for every $x \in X$.

Definition 8.3. A liner X is called *hypersymmetric* if for every triangle abc in X there exists a hyperfixed involutive automorphism $A : X \rightarrow X$ such that $Aabc = cba$.

In this definition by $Aabc$ we understand the ordered triple $(A(a), A(b), A(c))$.

Theorem 8.4 ([1, 36.2.11]). *An affine regular liner is shear if and only if it is hypersymmetric.*

9. PARALLEL PROJECTIONS IN AFFINE SPACES

We recall that an *affine space* is any 3-long affine regular liner of rank ≥ 3 . By [1, 3.7.2], every affine space X is Playfair and hence every line L in X is spreading and determines the direction $L_{\parallel} \in \partial X$. For a direction $\delta \in \partial X$ in an affine space X and a point $x \in X$ we denote by $\overline{x\delta}$ a unique line in the spread δ that contains the point x .

We say that a direction $\delta \in \partial X$ is *subparallel* to a flat $A \subseteq X$ if every line $L \in \delta$ is subparallel to A . By [1, 6.5.6], a direction $\delta \in \partial X$ is subparallel to a flat A if and only if some line $L \in \delta$ is subparallel to A if and only if some line $L \in \delta$ is contained in the flat A .

A relation $R \subseteq X \times X$ on a liner X is *flat* if for every flat $A, B \subseteq X$, the sets

$$R[A] := \{y : \exists a \in A (a, y) \in R\} \quad \text{and} \quad R^{-1}[B] := \{x : \exists b \in B (a, b) \in R\}$$

are flat in X .

Proposition 9.1 ([1, 13.1.5]). *Let X be an affine space. For two flats $A, B \subseteq X$ and a direction $\delta \in \partial X$, the relation*

$$F := \{(x, y) \in A \times B : \overline{x\delta} = \overline{y\delta}\}$$

is flat and has the following properties.

- (1) *If the direction δ is not subparallel to the flat B , then F is a function.*
- (2) *If F is a nonempty function, then the direction δ is not subparallel to B .*
- (3) *If the direction δ is not subparallel to the flat A , then F^{-1} is a function.*
- (4) *If F^{-1} is a nonempty function, then the direction δ is not subparallel to A .*
- (5) *If $A \cap B = \emptyset$, then F is an injective function and $\text{dom}[F], \text{rng}[F]$ are disjoint parallel flats in X .*

Definition 9.2. Let X be an affine space. A function $F \subseteq X \times X$ is called a *parallel projection in a direction $\delta \in \partial X$* if

$$F = \{(x, y) \in \text{dom}[F] \times \text{rng}[F] : \overline{x\delta} = \overline{y\delta}\}.$$

A function $F \subseteq X \times X$ is called *parallel projection* if F is a parallel projection in some direction $\delta \in \partial X$. If $\text{dom}[F]$ and $\text{rng}[F]$ are lines in X , then F is called a *line projection in X* .

Applying Proposition 9.1, we obtain the following general example of a flat parallel projection.

Example 9.3 ([1, 13.2.2]). Let A, B be two flats in an affine regular liner X and a direction $\delta \in \partial X$ is not subparallel to B . Then

$$F := \{(x, y) \in A \times B : \overline{x\delta} = \overline{y\delta}\}$$

is a flat parallel projection in the direction δ . The function F is injective if the direction δ is not subparallel to the flat A . If $A \cap B = \emptyset$, then the function F is injective and flats $\text{dom}[F], \text{rng}[F]$ are disjoint and parallel.

Example 9.4 ([1, 13.2.3]). For every flat $A \neq X$ in a 3-ranked space (X, \mathbb{L}) , the identity map 1_A is a parallel projection.

Sometimes it will be convenient to use the following alternative description of parallel projections (that does not involve directions).

Proposition 9.5 ([1, 13.2.4]). *Let X be an affine space. A function $F \subseteq X \times X$ is a parallel projection (in a direction $\delta \in \partial X$) if and only if there exists a line L (with $L \in \delta$) such that*

$$F = \{(x, y) \in \text{dom}[F] \times \text{rng}[F] : \overline{xy} \parallel L\}.$$

Proposition 9.6 ([1, 13.2.5]). *Let X be an affine space and $F \subseteq X \times X$ be a parallel projection in a direction $\delta \in \partial X$.*

- (1) *For every $x \in \text{dom}[F] \cap \text{rng}[F]$ we have $F(x) = x$.*
- (2) *If $\text{dom}[F] = \text{rng}[F]$, then F is the identity map of the set $\text{dom}[F] = \text{rng}[F]$.*
- (3) *The function F is flat if and only if $\text{dom}[F]$ and $\text{rng}[F]$ are flats.*
- (4) *If $\text{dom}[F]$ and $\text{rng}[F]$ are disjoint flats, then the function F is injective and the flats $\text{dom}[F]$ and $\text{rng}[F]$ are parallel.*
- (5) *If $\text{dom}[F]$ and $\text{rng}[F]$ are two lines, then the function F is injective.*

Definition 9.7. A parallel projection $P \subseteq X \times X$ in a liner X is called a

- a *parallel shift* if $\text{dom}[P]$ and $\text{rng}[P]$ are parallel flats in X ;
- a *parallel translation* if T is the composition of finitely many parallel shifts.

By Proposition 9.6(2,4), every parallel shift S in an affine space X is a bijective flat function between the parallel flats $\text{dom}[S]$ and $\text{rng}[S]$. Consequently, every parallel translation T in X is a bijective flat function between the flats $\text{dom}[T]$ and $\text{rng}[T]$.

Proposition 9.8 ([1, 13.2.7]). *For every parallel translation $T \subseteq X \times X$ in an affine space X , the flats $\text{dom}[T]$ and $\text{rng}[T]$ are parallel.*

10. LINE PROJECTIONS IN AFFINE SPACES

Definition 10.1. A *line projection* in a liner X is a parallel projection $P \subseteq X \times X$ such that $\text{dom}[P]$ and $\text{rng}[P]$ are lines in X .

A *line bijection* is a bijective function between two lines in a liner. By Proposition 9.6, every line projection P in a liner X is a line bijection and hence P is an element of the monoid \mathcal{I}_X^ℓ (consisting of the identity map of X and all bijections between flats of rank ≤ 2 in X). The smallest submonoid of \mathcal{I}_X^ℓ that contains all line projections in X is denoted by \mathcal{I}_X^\times . Line bijections that belong to the monoid \mathcal{I}_X^\times are called *line affinities*. Alternatively, line affinities can be defined as follows.

Definition 10.2. A line bijection F in a liner X is called a *line affinity* if F is the composition of finitely many line projections in X .

Proposition 9.1(5) implies the following important fact.

Proposition 10.3 ([1, 13.3.6]). *For every line projection P in an affine liner, the lines $\text{dom}[P]$ and $\text{rng}[P]$ are either concurrent or parallel.*

Proposition 10.3 motivates the following definition.

Definition 10.4. A line projection P in a liner is called

- a *line shift* if $\text{dom}[P] \parallel \text{rng}[P]$;
- a *line shear* if $\text{dom}[P] \cap \text{rng}[P]$ is a singleton, called the *shear center* of P ;

Propositions 10.3 imply that every line projection in an affine regular space X is either a line shift or a line shear.

For a liner X we denote by $\mathcal{I}_X^\#$ the smallest submonoid of \mathcal{I}_X^\times , containing all line shifts in X . Line bijections that belong to the monoid $\mathcal{I}_X^\#$ are called *line translations*. Alternatively, line translations can be defined as follows.

Definition 10.5. A line bijection F in a liner X is called a *line translation* if F is the finite composition of line shifts.

Therefore, for every liner X , we obtain the following increasing chain of monoids:

$$\mathcal{I}_X^\# \subseteq \mathcal{I}_X^\times \subseteq \mathcal{I}_X^\ell \subseteq \mathcal{I}_X.$$

For every line L in a liner X , the subset

$$\mathcal{I}_X^\#[L] := \{T \in \mathcal{I}_X^\# : \text{dom}[T] = L = \text{rng}[T]\}$$

of all line translations $T : L \rightarrow L$ is a subgroup of the semigroup $\mathcal{I}_X^\#$, called the *group of line translations* of the line L . The structure of the groups $\mathcal{I}_X^\#[L]$ will be discussed in Section 14 of this survey.

Recall that two lines in a liner are *paraconcurrent* if they are parallel or concurrent.

Theorem 10.6 ([1, 13.3.12]). *For every paraconcurrent lines L, L' in an affine space X and every points $a \in L \setminus L'$ and $a' \in L' \setminus L$, there exists a unique line projection $P : L \rightarrow L'$ such that $P(a) = a'$.*

For concurrent lines in affine spaces, Theorem 10.6 implies the following corollary on the existence of line shears with prescribed values.

Corollary 10.7 ([1, 13.3.13]). *For every lines L, L' in an affine space and points $o \in L \cap L'$, $a \in L \setminus L'$ and $a' \in L' \setminus L$, there exists a unique line shear $R : L \rightarrow L'$ such that $Roa = oa'$.*

Next, we derive from Theorem 10.6 two corollaries on the existence of line shifts and line translations in affine spaces.

Corollary 10.8 ([1, 13.3.14]). *For every line L in an affine space X and every points $x \in L$ and $x' \in X \setminus L$ there exists a unique line shift S in X such that $\text{dom}[S] = L$ and $S(x) = x'$.*

Corollary 10.9 ([1, 13.3.15]). *For every parallel lines L, L' in an affine space X and every points $x \in L$ and $x' \in L'$ there exists a line translation $T : L \rightarrow L'$ such that $T(x) = x'$. Moreover, the line translation T is the composition of two line shifts in X .*

The following proposition implies that for an affine space X , the monoid \mathcal{I}_X^\times is generated by line shears.

Proposition 10.10 ([1, 13.3.16]). *Let S be a line shift in an affine space X . Then for every points $a \in \text{dom}[S]$ and $b' \in \text{rng}[S] \setminus \{S(a)\}$ there exist unique line shears $R_1 : \text{dom}[S] \rightarrow \overline{ab'}$ and $R_2 : \overline{ab'} \rightarrow \text{rng}[S]$ such that $S = R_2R_1$.*

The following theorem shows that a bijections between two flats of rank ≤ 1 in an affine space can be represented as compositions of two line shifts or two line shears.

Theorem 10.11 ([1, 13.3.17]). *Let $F : A \rightarrow B$ be a bijection between sets of cardinality $|A| = |B| \leq 1$ in an affine space X . Then*

- (1) $F = S_2S_1$ for some line shifts S_1, S_2 in X ;
- (2) $F = R_2R_1$ for some line shears R_1, R_2 in X ;
- (3) $F = R_3S_3$ for some line shift S_3 and line shear R_3 in X ;
- (4) $F = S_4R_4$ for some line shear R_4 and line shift S_4 in X .

Theorem 10.11(1) implies

Corollary 10.12 ([1, 13.3.18]). *For any affine space X , the monoids $\mathcal{I}_X^\# \subseteq \mathcal{I}_X^\times$ contain all bijections between subsets of cardinality ≤ 1 in X .*

Theorem 10.13 ([1, 13.3.19]). *For every affine space X and points $a, b, a', b' \in X$ with $a \neq b$ and $a' \neq b'$, there exists a line affinity $A : \overline{ab} \rightarrow \overline{a'b'}$ such that $F(a) = a'$ and $F(b) = b'$. Moreover, the line affinity A is the composition of two line shears or two line shifts.*

11. LINE TRANSLATIONS IN THALESIAN AFFINE SPACES

Theorem 11.1 ([1, 13.4.1]). *An affine space X is Thalesian if and only if for any line shifts $F : L_1 \rightarrow L_2$ and $G : L_2 \rightarrow L_3$ between lines L_1, L_2, L_3 in X with $L_1 \neq L_3$, the composition $GF : L_1 \rightarrow L_3$ is a line shift.*

Corollary 11.2 ([1, 13.4.4]). *Let X be a Thalesian affine space. Every line translation T in X is the composition of two line shifts in X .*

Theorem 11.3 ([1, 13.4.5]). *An affine space X is Thalesian if and only if for every line L in X and every points $x \in L$ and $x' \in X$ there exists a unique line translation T in X such that $\text{dom}[T] = L$ and $T(x) = x'$.*

12. TRANSLATIONS VERSUS LINE TRANSLATIONS

In this section we study the interplay between translations and line shifts in affine spaces.

Proposition 12.1 ([1, 13.5.1]). *Let $T : X \rightarrow X$ be a translation of an affine space X . For every line $L \subseteq X$ with $T[L] \neq L$, the restriction $T|_L$ is a line shift of X .*

Proposition 12.2 ([1, 13.5.2]). *Let X be an affine space such that $\|\{T(o) : T \in \text{Tra}(X)\}\| \neq 2$ for some point $o \in X$. Then for every translation $T \in \text{Tra}(X)$ and every line $L \subseteq X$, the restriction $T|_L : L \rightarrow T[L]$ is a line translation.*

Question 12.3 ([1, 13.5.3]). *Is there a translation $T : X \rightarrow X$ of an affine space X such that for some line $L \subseteq X$, the restriction $T|_L$ is not a line translation?*

Theorem 12.4 ([1, 13.5.5]). *For every line translation S in an affine space X and every translation $T : X \rightarrow X$ with $T[\text{dom}[S]] = \text{dom}[S]$, we have $TS = ST$.*

The following important theorem was proved as Lemma 2.1 in the paper [5] of Andrew Gleason.

Theorem 12.5 (Gleason; [1, 13.5.6]). *Let X be an affine space, L be a line in X . For a bijection $P : L \rightarrow L$ the following conditions are equivalent:*

- (1) *there exists a translation $T : X \rightarrow X$ such that $T|_L = P$;*
- (2) *for every line translation $S : L \rightarrow L$ we have $SP = PS$;*
- (3) *for every line $\Lambda \subseteq X$ and line shifts $A : L \rightarrow \Lambda$ and $B : \Lambda \rightarrow L$ we have $(BA)P = P(BA)$;*
- (4) *for every line $\Lambda \subseteq X$ and line shifts $A, B : \Lambda \rightarrow L$, we have $A^{-1}PA = B^{-1}PB$;*

Let us recall that a liner X is called *translation* if for every points $x, y \in X$ there exists a translation $T : X \rightarrow X$ such that $T(x) = y$.

Theorem 12.6 ([1, 13.5.10]). *For an affine space X , the following conditions are equivalent:*

- (1) *the liner X is translation;*
- (2) *for every line shift $S : L \rightarrow \Lambda$ between lines L and Λ in X , there exists a translation $T : X \rightarrow X$ such that $S = T|_L$;*
- (3) *for every line translation $S : L \rightarrow \Lambda$ between lines L and Λ in X , there exists a translation $T : X \rightarrow X$ such that $S = T|_L$;*
- (4) *for every line translation $S : L \rightarrow L$ of a line L in X , there exists a translation $T : X \rightarrow X$ such that $S = T|_L$.*

Theorem 12.7 ([1, 13.5.11]). *For an affine space X , the following conditions are equivalent:*

- (1) *X is translation;*
- (2) $\mathcal{I}_X^\# = \{1_X\} \cup \{T|_L : T \in \text{Tra}(X), \overline{L} = L \subseteq X, \|L\| \leq 2\}$;

- (3) every subgroup in the semigroup $\mathcal{I}_X^\#$ is commutative;
 (4) for every line shifts A, B, C, D in X with $\text{dom}[A] = \text{rng}[B] = \text{dom}[C] = \text{rng}[D]$ we have $(DC)(BA) = (BA)(DC)$.

13. ∂ -TRANSLATION AFFINE SPACES

Definition 13.1. An affine space X is defined to be *∂ -translation* if for every spread of parallel lines $\delta \in \partial X$, there exists a translation $T : X \rightarrow X$ such that $\{\overline{xy} : xy \in T\} = \delta$.

Theorem 13.2 ([1, 13.6.2]). *An affine space X of prime order is translation if and only if it is ∂ -translation.*

Problem 13.3 ([1, 13.6.1]). *Is every ∂ -translation finite Playfair plane translation?*

Proposition 13.4 ([1, 13.6.4]). *If an affine space X is ∂ -translation, then*

- (1) the translation group $\text{Tra}(X)$ of X is commutative and has cardinality $|\text{Tra}(X)| \geq 2 + |X|_2$.
 (2) If $\text{Tra}(X)$ contains a non-identity element of finite order, then $\text{Tra}(X)$ is elementary Abelian.

Let us recall that for a line L in a liner X , we denote by $\mathcal{I}_X^\#[L]$ the group of all line translation $T : L \rightarrow L$. For a group G its *center* is the set

$$Z(G) := \bigcap_{x \in G} \{z \in G : x \cdot z = z \cdot x\}$$

of all elements of G that commute with all other elements of G . Gleason's Theorem 12.5 implies the following group characterizations of translation and ∂ -translation affine spaces.

Corollary 13.5 ([1, 13.6.5]). *An affine space X is*

- (1) translation if and only if for every line $L \subseteq X$, the group $\mathcal{I}_X^\#[L]$ is commutative;
 (2) ∂ -translation if and only if for every line $L \subseteq X$ the group $\mathcal{I}_X^\#[L]$ has non-trivial center.

Corollary 13.5(2) motivates the problem of detecting groups with non-trivial center. A classical result in this direction is due to Burnside (1897). A number $n \in \mathbb{N}$ is called a *prime power* if $n = p^k$ for some prime number p and some number $k \in \mathbb{N}$.

Theorem 13.6 (Burnside; [1, 13.6.6]). *A finite group G has non-trivial center if the order of G is a prime power.*

14. THE GROUP OF LINE TRANSLATIONS

In this section we survey some basic results on the structure of the group $\mathcal{I}_X^\#[L]$ of line translations of a line L in a Playfair plane X . First, we describe generators of the group $\mathcal{I}_X^\#[L]$. We say that a group G is *generated by a set $S \subseteq G$* if G coincides with the smallest subgroup of G that contains the set S .

Given any line $\Lambda \in L_\parallel$ and any direction $\delta \in \partial X \setminus \{L_\parallel\}$, consider the line shift $\delta_{\Lambda, L} : L \rightarrow \Lambda$ assigning to every point $x \in L$ the unique point $y \in \Lambda \cap \overline{x\delta}$ (the point y exists because X is a Playfair plane and $L \notin \delta$).

For two directions $\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \in \partial X \setminus \{L_\parallel\}$, consider the subset

$$\mathcal{I}_X^\#[L; \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}] = \{\mathbf{u}_{L, \Lambda} \mathbf{v}_{\Lambda, L} : \Lambda \in L_\parallel\}$$

of the group $\mathcal{I}_X^\#[L]$.

Proposition 14.1 ([1, 13.7.2]). *For every line L in a Playfair plane X , any distinct directions $\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \in \partial X \setminus \partial L_\parallel$ and any point $o \in L$, the function $\alpha : \mathcal{I}_X^\#[L; \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}] \rightarrow L$, $\alpha : T \mapsto T(o)$, is bijective and hence $|\mathcal{I}_X^\#[L; \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}]| = |L| = |X|_2$.*

Lemma 14.2 ([1, 13.7.3]). *For every line L in an affine space X , the group $\mathcal{I}_X^\#[L]$ is generated by the set*

$$\bigcup_{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \in \partial X \setminus \{L_\parallel\}} \mathcal{I}_X^\#[L; \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}].$$

For two subsets A, B of a group G we denote by

$$A \cdot B := \{a \cdot b : (a, b) \in A \times B\}$$

their pointwise product in G .

Lemma 14.3 ([1, 13.7.4]). *For every line L in a Playfair plane X and directions $\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}, \boldsymbol{\delta} \in \partial X \setminus \{L_{\parallel}\}$,*

$$\mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L; \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}] \subseteq \mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L; \mathbf{u}, \boldsymbol{\delta}] \cdot \mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L; \boldsymbol{\delta}, \mathbf{v}].$$

Lemmas 14.2 and 14.3 imply the following corollary.

Corollary 14.4 ([1, 13.7.5]). *For every line L in a Playfair plane X and every direction $\boldsymbol{\delta} \in \partial X \setminus \{L_{\parallel}\}$, the group $\mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L]$ is generated by the set*

$$\bigcup_{\mathbf{u} \in \partial X \setminus \{L_{\parallel}\}} (\mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L; \mathbf{u}, \boldsymbol{\delta}] \cup \mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L; \boldsymbol{\delta}, \mathbf{u}]).$$

Lemma 14.5 ([1, 13.7.6]). *Let L be a line in a Playfair plane X and $\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}, \boldsymbol{\delta} \in \partial X \setminus \{L_{\parallel}\}$ be directions such that the sets $\mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L; \mathbf{v}, \boldsymbol{\delta}], \mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L; \boldsymbol{\delta}, \mathbf{u}], \mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L; \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{u}]$ are subgroups of the group $\mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L]$. Then*

$$\mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L; \mathbf{u}, \boldsymbol{\delta}] \cdot \mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L; \boldsymbol{\delta}, \mathbf{v}] = \mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L; \boldsymbol{\delta}, \mathbf{v}] \cdot \mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L; \mathbf{u}, \boldsymbol{\delta}].$$

Proposition 14.6 ([1, 13.7.7]). *Let L be a line in a Playfair plane X such that for every directions $\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \in \partial X \setminus \{L_{\parallel}\}$, the set $\mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L; \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}]$ is a subgroup of the group $\mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L]$. If the cardinal $n := |X|_2$ is finite, then the cardinality of the group $\mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L]$ divides the the number n^{n-1} .*

Proposition 14.6 and Theorem 13.6 imply the following corollary.

Corollary 14.7 ([1, 13.7.8]). *Let L be a line in a Playfair plane X such that for every directions $\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \in \partial X \setminus \{L_{\parallel}\}$ the set $\mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L; \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}]$ is a subgroup of the group $\mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L]$. If $|X|_2$ is a prime power, then the group $\mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L]$ has non-trivial center.*

Corollaries 14.7 and 13.5 imply the following main result of this section, due to Gleason [5].

Theorem 14.8 (Gleason; [1, 13.7.9]). *A Playfair plane X is ∂ -translation whenever $|X|_2$ is a prime power and for every line $L \subset X$ and distinct directions $\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \in \partial X \setminus \{L_{\parallel}\}$, the set $\mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L; \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}]$ is a subgroup of the group $\mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L]$.*

Problem 14.9 ([1, 13.7.10]). *Is every ∂ -translation finite Playfair plane translation?*

We shall also need a modification of Gleason's Theorem 14.8 in which the groups $\mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L; \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}]$ are replaced by groups $\mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L; \mathbf{h}, \Lambda]$, defined as follows.

For two parallel lines L, Λ in a Playfair plane X and a direction $\mathbf{h} \in \partial X \setminus \{L_{\parallel}\}$, consider the set

$$\mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L; \mathbf{h}, \Lambda] := \{\mathbf{u}_{L, \Lambda} \mathbf{h}_{\Lambda, L} : \mathbf{u} \in \partial X \setminus \{L_{\parallel}\}\}.$$

Proposition 14.10 ([1, 13.7.11]). *For any parallel lines L, Λ in a Playfair plane X , any direction $\mathbf{h} \in \partial X \setminus L_{\parallel}$ and point $o \in L$, the function $\alpha : \mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L; \mathbf{h}, \Lambda] \rightarrow L$, $\alpha : T \mapsto T(o)$, is bijective and hence $|\mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L; \mathbf{h}, \Lambda]| = |L| = |X|_2$.*

Lemma 14.11 ([1, 13.7.12]). *For every line L in a Playfair plane X and directions $\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{h} \in \partial X \setminus \{L_{\parallel}\}$,*

$$\mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L; \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}] \subseteq \bigcup_{\Lambda \in L_{\parallel}} \mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L; \mathbf{h}, \Lambda] \cdot (\mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L; \mathbf{h}, \Lambda])^{-1}.$$

Lemmas 14.2 and 14.11 imply the following corollary.

Corollary 14.12 ([1, 13.7.13]). *For every line L in a Playfair plane X and every direction $\mathbf{h} \in \partial X \setminus \{L_{\parallel}\}$, the group $\mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L]$ is generated by the set*

$$\bigcup_{\Lambda \in L_{\parallel}} \mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L; \mathbf{h}, \Lambda].$$

Lemma 14.13 ([1, 13.7.14]). *Let L be a line in a Playfair plane X , $A, B \in L_{\parallel}$ be two lines and $\mathbf{h} \in \partial X \setminus \{L_{\parallel}\}$ be a direction such that the sets $\mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L; \mathbf{h}, A], \mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L; \mathbf{h}, B], \mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[B; \mathbf{h}, A]$ are subgroups of the semigroup \mathcal{I}_X . Then*

$$\mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L; \mathbf{h}, A] \cdot \mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L; \mathbf{h}, B] = \mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L; \mathbf{h}, B] \cdot \mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L; \mathbf{h}, A].$$

Proposition 14.14 ([1, 13.7.15]). *Let \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{v} be two distinct directions in a Playfair plane X such that for every lines $L, \Lambda \in \mathbf{v}$, the set $\mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L; \mathbf{h}, \Lambda]$ is a subgroup of the semigroup $\mathcal{I}_X^{\#}$. If the cardinal $n := |X|_2$ is finite, then for every line $L \in \mathbf{v}$, the cardinality of the group $\mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L]$ divides the the number n^{n-1} .*

Proposition 14.14 and Theorem 13.6 imply the following corollary.

Corollary 14.15 ([1, 13.7.16]). *Let \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{v} be two distinct direction in a Playfair plane X such that for every lines $L, \Lambda \in \mathbf{v}$, the set $\mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L; \mathbf{h}, \Lambda]$ is a subgroup of the group $\mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L]$. If $|X|_2$ is a prime power, then for every $L \in \mathbf{v}$, the group $\mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L]$ has non-trivial center.*

Corollaries 14.15 and 13.5 imply the following modification of Gleason's Theorem 14.8.

Theorem 14.16 ([1, 13.7.17]). *A Playfair plane X is ∂ -translation whenever $|X|_2$ is a prime power and for distinct directions $\mathbf{h}, \mathbf{v} \in \partial X$, and every lines $L, \Lambda \in \mathbf{v}$, the set $\mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L; \mathbf{h}, \Lambda]$ is a subgroup of the group $\mathcal{I}_X^{\#}[L]$.*

15. LINE AFFINITIES AND IN AFFINE SPACES

Let us recall that a bijection $A : L \rightarrow \Lambda$ between two lines in an affine space X is called a *line affinity* if $A = P_1 \cdots P_n$ for some line projections P_1, \dots, P_n . A bijection $P : L \rightarrow L'$ between two lines L, L' is called a *line projection* if there exists a line Λ such that $P = \{(x, y) \in L \times L' : \overline{xy} \parallel \Lambda\}$. A line projection $P : L \rightarrow L'$ is called a *line shift* if $L \parallel L'$, and a *deftermline shear* if $L \cap L' = \{o\}$ for a unique point o , called the *shear center*.

Proposition 15.1 ([1, 15.1.1]). *For every line shear R in an affine space X and every point $o' \in X$, there exist line shifts S, S' and a line shear R' such that $R = S' R' S$ and $R'(o') = o'$.*

Corollary 15.2 ([1, 15.1.2]). *Let A be a line affinity in an affine space X . For every point $o \in X$, there exist line translations T_0, T_1, \dots, T_n and line shears R_1, \dots, R_n in X such that $A = T_n R_n T_{n-1} \cdots T_1 R_1 T_0$ and $R_i(o) = o$ for all $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$.*

Proposition 15.3 ([1, 15.2.1]). *Let R be a line shear in a Thalesian affine space X . For every line translation $T : \text{dom}[R] \rightarrow \text{dom}[R]$ the function $RTR^{-1} : \text{rng}[R] \rightarrow \text{rng}[R]$ is a line translation.*

Theorem 15.4 ([1, 15.2.2]). *Let A be a line affinity in a Thalesian affine space X . For every point $o \in X$, there exist line translations T, T' and line shears R_1, \dots, R_n in X such that $A = T' R_n R_{n-1} \cdots R_1 T$, and $R_i(o) = o$ for all $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$. Moreover, if $o \in \text{dom}[A]$, then T is the identity translation of $\text{dom}[A]$.*

16. LINE SHEARS AND LINE AFFINITIES IN DESARGUESIAN AFFINE SPACES

In this section we study the structure of compositions of line shears around the same point in a Desarguesian affine spaces. The following theorem is a “shear” counterpart of Theorem 11.1.

Theorem 16.1 ([1, 15.3.1]). *An affine space X is Desarguesian if and only if for any concurrent lines L_1, L_2, L_3 with $L_1 \neq L_3$ and every line shears $P : L_1 \rightarrow L_2$ and $R : L_2 \rightarrow L_3$, the composition $RP : L_1 \rightarrow L_3$ is a line shear.*

Corollary 16.2 ([1, 15.3.5]). *The composition of finitely many line shears around a point o in a Desarguesian affine space X is equal to the composition of two lines shears around the point o .*

Theorem 16.3 ([1, 15.4.3]). *Two line affinities in a Desarguesian affine space X coincide if and only if $\text{dom}[F] = \text{dom}[G]$, $\text{rng}[F] = \text{rng}[G]$ and $(F(x), F(y)) = (G(x), G(y))$ for some distinct points $x, y \in \text{dom}[F] = \text{dom}[G]$.*

Corollary 16.4 ([1, 15.4.4]). *An affine space X is Desarguesian if and only if for any points $x, x', y, y' \in X$ with $x \neq y$ and $x' \neq y'$ there exists a unique line affinity $A : \overline{xy} \rightarrow \overline{x'y'}$ such that $A(x) = x'$ and $A(y) = y'$.*

Corollary 16.5 ([1, 15.4.5]). *Every line affinity A in a Desarguesian affine space X is the composition of two line shears or two line shifts.*

Proposition 16.6 ([1, 15.4.6]). *Every line affinity A in a Desarguesian affine space X is the composition of three line shears.*

17. HOMOTHETIES VERSUS LINE SHEARS

Theorem 17.1 ([1, 15.5.1]). *Let X be an affine space and $H : X \rightarrow X$ be a homothety of X with center o . Then $HR = RH$ for every line shear R in X around the point o .*

The following theorem is a “shear” counterpart of the Gleason’s Theorem 12.5.

Theorem 17.2 ([1, 15.5.2]). *Let X be an affine space, L be a line in X and $o \in L$ be a point. For a bijection $A : L \rightarrow L$ with $A(o) = o$, the following conditions are equivalent:*

- (1) $A = H \setminus_L$ for some homothety $H : X \rightarrow X$;
- (2) for every line $\Lambda \subseteq X$ with $L \cap \Lambda = \{o\}$ and any line shears $P : L \rightarrow \Lambda$ and $R : \Lambda \rightarrow L$ we have $A(RP) = (RP)A$;
- (3) for every line $\Lambda \subseteq X$ with $L \cap \Lambda = \{o\}$ and any line shears $P, R : \Lambda \rightarrow L$, we have $P^{-1}AP = R^{-1}AR$.

18. CENTRAL PROJECTIONS IN LINERS

Definition 18.1. A function $F \subseteq X \times X$ in a liner X is called a *central projection with center o* if $F = \{(x, y) \in \text{dom}[F] \times \text{rng}[F] : y \in \overline{ox}\}$. The point o is called a *center* of the central projection. A central projection F whose domain and range are lines in X is called a *perspectivity between lines* in X or just a *line perspectivity* in X . In this case, the point o is called a *perspectivity center* of the line perspectivity F .

Example 18.2. For every flats A, B in X and point $o \in X \setminus (A \cup B)$, the relation

$$F := \{(x, y) \in A \times B : y \in \overline{xo}\}$$

is a central projection with the center o . If A, B are two coplanar lines and $o \in \overline{AB}$, then F is a line perspectivity with $\text{dom}[F] = A$ and $\text{rng}[F] = B$.

Example 18.3. For every flat $A \neq X$ in a liner X , the identity bijection $1_A : A \rightarrow A$ is a central projection (with an arbitrary center $o \in X \setminus A$).

Proposition 18.4 ([1, 22.2.4]). *Let X be a liner and P be a central projection with center o such that the sets $\text{dom}[P]$ and $\text{rng}[P]$ are flat in X .*

- (1) *The point o belongs to $\text{dom}[P] \cup \text{rng}[P]$ if and only if $\text{rng}[P] = \{o\}$.*
- (2) *If $o \notin \text{dom}[P] \cup \text{rng}[P]$, then the function P is injective and P^{-1} is a central projection with center o .*
- (3) *P is a flat function such that $P(x) = x$ for all $x \in \text{dom}[P] \cap \text{rng}[P]$.*
- (4) *If $|\text{dom}[P]| > 1$ and $\text{dom}[P] \neq \text{rng}[P]$, then the center o of the central projection P is uniquely determined by P .*

Corollary 18.5 ([1, 22.2.5]). *Every line perspectivity P in a liner X is a line bijection such that the lines $\text{dom}[P], \text{rng}[P]$ are coplanar and $P(x) = x$ for all $x \in \text{dom}[P] \cap \text{rng}[P]$. If $\text{dom}[P] \neq \text{rng}[P]$, then the center o of the central projection P is uniquely determined by P and belongs to $\overline{\text{dom}[P] \cup \text{rng}[P]} \setminus (\text{dom}[P] \cup \text{rng}[P])$.*

Definition 18.6. A *line projectivity* in a liner X is a bijection $P : L \rightarrow \Lambda$ between lines $L, \Lambda \subseteq X$ such that P can be written as the composition of finitely many line perspectivities in X .

Exercise 18.7 ([1, 22.2.7]). Prove that for every line projectivity P in an affine space X , the lines $\text{dom}[P]$ and $\text{rng}[P]$ are parallel.

Exercise* 18.8 ([1, 22.2.8]). Prove that every line projectivity in a Desarguesian affine space is a line affinity.

A triple xyz of points of a liner is called a *colinear triple* if $|\{x, y, z\}| = 3$ and $\|\{x, y, z\}\| = 2$. So, a colinear triple consists of three colinear pairwise distinct points.

Theorem 18.9 ([1, 22.3.1]). *For any colinear triples $x_1x_2x_3$ and $z_1z_2z_3$ in a projective space X , there exists a line projectivity P such that $P(x_i) = z_i$ for all $i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ and P is the composition of two or three line perspectivities.*

19. LINE PROJECTIVITIES IN DESARGUESIAN PROJECTIVE SPACES

Theorem 19.1 ([1, 22.4.1]). *A projective space X is Desarguesian if and only if for any concurrent lines A, B, C , with $A \neq C$ and line perspectivities $P : A \rightarrow B$ and $R : B \rightarrow C$, the composition $RP : A \rightarrow C$ is a line perspectivity.*

Lemma 19.2 ([1, 22.4.2]). *Let A, B, C, D be concurrent lines in a Desarguesian projective space X such that $A \neq C \neq D$. For any line perspectivities $P : A \rightarrow B$ and $P' : B \rightarrow C$ and any point $o \in X \setminus (A \cup D)$, there exist line perspectivities $R : A \rightarrow D$ and $R' : D \rightarrow C$ such that $P'P = R'R$ and o is the perspectivity center of the line perspectivity R .*

Lemma 19.3 ([1, 22.4.3]). *Let X be a Desarguesian projective space, L, Λ, L' be lines with $L \cap \Lambda \cap L' = \emptyset$, and $P : L \rightarrow \Lambda$, $P' : \Lambda \rightarrow L'$ be two line perspectivities. For every line Λ' such that $L \cap \Lambda' \neq \emptyset \neq \Lambda' \cap \Lambda \cap L'$ and $L \neq \Lambda' \neq L'$, there exist line perspectivities $R : L \rightarrow \Lambda'$ and $R' : \Lambda' \rightarrow L'$ such that $P'P = R'R$.*

The following lemma is a symmetric version of Lemma 19.3.

Lemma 19.4 ([1, 22.4.4]). *Let X be a Desarguesian projective space, L, Λ, L' be lines with $L \cap \Lambda \cap L' = \emptyset$, and $P : L \rightarrow \Lambda$, $P' : \Lambda \rightarrow L'$ be two line perspectivities. For every line Λ' such that $\Lambda' \cap L' \neq \emptyset \neq L \cap \Lambda \cap \Lambda'$ and $L \neq \Lambda' \neq L'$, there exist line perspectivities $R : L \rightarrow \Lambda'$ and $R' : \Lambda' \rightarrow L'$ such that $P'P = R'R$.*

Lemma 19.5 ([1, 22.4.5]). *Let P_1, P_2, P_3 be three line perspectivities in a Desarguesian projective space X such that $\text{rng}[P_1] = \text{dom}[P_2]$ and $\text{rng}[P_2] = \text{dom}[P_3]$. If $\text{dom}[P_1] \cap \text{dom}[P_2] \cap \text{dom}[P_3] \neq \emptyset$ or $\text{rng}[P_1] \cap \text{rng}[P_2] \cap \text{rng}[P_3] \neq \emptyset$, then $P_3P_2P_1 = R'R$ for some line perspectivities R and R' in X .*

Lemma 19.6 ([1, 22.4.6]). *Let P_1, P_2, P_3 be three line perspectivities in a Desarguesian projective space X such that $\text{rng}[P_1] = \text{dom}[P_2]$ and $\text{rng}[P_2] = \text{dom}[P_3]$. If $\text{dom}[P_1] \neq \text{rng}[P_3]$, then $P_3P_2P_1 = R'R$ for some line perspectivities R and R' in X .*

The following theorem was first proved by Hessenberg [6].

Theorem 19.7 (Hessenberg; [1, 22.4.7]). *Every line projectivity P in a Desarguesian projective space is the composition of three line perspectivities. Moreover, if $\text{dom}[P] \neq \text{rng}[P]$, then P is the composition of two line perspectivities.*

20. LINE PROJECTIVITIES IN PAPPIAN PROJECTIVE SPACES

The following theorem and corollaries are usually attributed to Pappus of Alexandria (≈ 320).

Theorem 20.1 ([1, 22.5.1]). *A line projectivity P in a Pappian projective space is a line perspectivity if and only if $\text{dom}[P] \cap \text{rng}[P] \neq \emptyset$ and $P(x) = x$ for every $x \in \text{dom}[P] \cap \text{rng}[P]$.*

Corollary 20.2 ([1, 22.5.2]). *Every line projectivity between distinct lines in a Pappian projective space is the composition of two line perspectivities.*

Corollary 20.3 ([1, 22.5.3]). *A line projectivity P in a Pappian projective space X is the identity map of the line $\text{dom}[P] = \text{rng}[P]$ if and only if the set $\text{Fix}(P) := \{x \in \text{dom}[P] : P(x) = x\}$ contains at least three points.*

Theorem 20.4 ([1, 22.5.4]). *A projective space X is Pappian if and only if for every colinear triples xyz and $x'y'z'$ in X there exists a unique line projectivity P such that $Pxyz = x'y'z'$.*

REFERENCES

- [1] T. Banakh, *Linear Geometry and Algebra*, (2025); <https://arxiv.org/abs/2506.14060>.
- [2] T. Banakh, I. Hetman, V. Pshyk, A. Ravsky, *Linear Geomery: flats, ranks, regularity, parallelity*, preprint (2025); (<https://arxiv.org/abs/2511.19455>).
- [3] T. Banakh, I. Hetman, V. Pshyk, A. Ravsky, *Linear Geomery: completions and projectivizations*, preprint (2025); (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1792042>).
- [4] T. Banakh, I. Hetman, O. Ilchuk, V. Pshyk, *Linear Geomery: Desargues, Pappus, Thales*, preprint (2025); (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17920520>).
- [5] A.M. Gleason, *Finite Fano planes*, Amer. J. Math. **78** (1956), 797–807.
- [6] G. Hessenberg, *Beweis des Desarguesschen Satzes aus dem Pascalschen*, Math. Ann. **61** (1905), 161–172.
- [7] G. Pickert, *Nichtkommutative cartesische Gruppen*, Arch. Math. **3** (1952), 335–342.

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